

**COOPERATIVE INTERACTION BETWEEN
METALLOSURFACTANTS, DERIVED FROM THE
[Ru(2,2'-bpy)₃]²⁺ COMPLEX, AND DNA**

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ABSTRACT

With the idea of improving and advancing the design and preparation of new reagents based on cationic surfactants for gene therapy, two luminescent metallosurfactants derived from the $[\text{Ru}(2,2'\text{-bpy})_3]^{2+}$ complex were synthesized. Their interaction with DNA and the effect they exert on the conformation of the polynucleotide were studied by using different techniques. The equilibrium binding constants, K_b , of the two surfactants to DNA were obtained at different molar ratios $X=[\text{surfactant}]/[\text{DNA}]$. The observed sigmoidal dependence of K_b on X confirms the cooperative character of the binding. After the addition of a determined surfactant concentration, the condensation of the polymer was observed. The amount of surfactant needed to produce this conformational change is lower for the double stranded surfactant than for the single chain surfactant due to a stronger hydrophobic interaction. The addition of α -cyclodextrin molecules to the metallosurfactant/DNA solutions results in polynucleotide decompaction, which confirms the importance of the hydrophobic interactions in the condensation of the polynucleotide. Results also show the importance of choosing both a proper system to study and the most seeming measuring technique to use. It is demonstrated that, in some cases, the use of several techniques is desirable to obtain reliable and accurate results.

Keywords: DNA, cooperative mode, condensation of DNA, metallosurfactant, cyclodextrin.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the last few decades the use of non-viral vectors in gene therapy (chemical method) has shown to be of interest since it avoids the secondary effects that the presence of viruses produces in the organisms. The interaction of some non-viral vectors with DNA results in the formation of DNA/vector complexes, which possess a globular structure and protects the nucleic acid from the restriction enzymes (endonucleases) attack, facilitating its diffusion into the cell cytoplasm. Many agents, including polypeptides [1,2], micelles [3], liposomes [4], histones [5], cationic vesicles [6] or nanoparticles [7] can cause the collapse of DNA molecules into a more compact structure. In the last few years, non-viral vectors containing coordination metal compounds were used [8-10]. So, for example, surfactants with a hydrophobic tail and a d- or f-block metal complex in the hydrophilic head were designed and synthesized. This type of amphiphilic compound is known as metallosurfactant. The presence of transition metal complexes in the surfactant structure is of interest because their physical properties are transferred to the amphiphilic molecule [11]. Particularly, ruthenium metallosurfactants are of considerable interest due to their applications in photochemistry or inorganic pharmacology [12,13]. Furthermore, it is important to indicate their potential anticancer character [14,15].

Bearing this in mind, two surfactants derived from the tris(2,2'-bipyridine) ruthenium (II) complex were synthesized and characterized: the double-tailed $[\text{Ru}(2,2'\text{-bipy})_2(4,4'\text{-(C}_{11}\text{H}_{23})_2\text{-2,2}'\text{-bipy})]^{2+}$ complex (RuC11C11) and the mono-tailed $[\text{Ru}(2,2'\text{-bipy})_2(4\text{-(CH}_3\text{)-4}'\text{-(C}_{11}\text{H}_{23})\text{-2,2}'\text{-bipy})]^{2+}$ complex (RuC1C11), see Figure 1. The interactions of these complexes with DNA were studied and the equilibrium binding constants were estimated. Results show the cooperative character of the

metallo-surfactant/DNA interactions, which results in the compaction of the polynucleotide.

It is worth noting that during the transfection process, once inside the cell, DNA should be decompacted to be accessible to the cell machinery responsible for translating the enclosed information. Therefore, it is desirable to achieve a reversible DNA condensation process. A representative class of molecules capable of modulating protein-surfactant and DNA-surfactant interactions are the cyclodextrins, CD, which possess a relatively non-polar cavity in their structure, thereby allowing formation of inclusion complexes with hydrophobic guests of suitable size, including surfactants [16]. With this in mind, the reversibility of the DNA compaction by the metallo-surfactants prepared in this work was investigated in the presence of α -cyclodextrin, α -CD.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials.

Chemicals were obtained from commercial sources (all R grade) and used as supplied or purified by distillation prior to use. Calf thymus DNA sodium salt, sodium chloride and sodium peroxodisulfate were purchased from Fluka. Polynucleotide concentration, given by phosphate groups, was determined spectrophotometrically from the known molar absorption data of $6600 \text{ mol}^{-1}\text{dm}^3\text{cm}^{-1}$ at 260nm [17]. An average number of base pairs per DNA molecule of 10000 bp was obtained from an agarose gel electrophoresis test using ethidium bromide. The ratios in absorbance at 260 and 280 nm of the solutions were found to be between 1.7 and 1.8, which suggested the absence of proteins [18].

Ethidium bromide and α -cyclodextrin were obtained from Sigma. The latter was dried at 80°C for at least 12h prior to use.

The ruthenium complexes $[\text{Ru}(2,2'\text{-bipy})_2(4,4'\text{-(C}_{11}\text{H}_{23})_2\text{-}2,2'\text{-bipy})][\text{PF}_6]_2$, **RuC11C11**, and $[\text{Ru}(2,2'\text{-bipy})_2(4\text{-(CH}_3\text{)-}4'\text{-(C}_{11}\text{H}_{23})\text{-}2,2'\text{-bipy})][\text{PF}_6]_2$, **RuC1C11**, were synthesized (see Figure 1) under a dry, oxygen-free, nitrogen atmosphere using standard Schlenk techniques. The water used for the preparation of solutions, obtained from a Millipore Milli-Q system, had a conductivity $< 10^{-6}$ S m⁻¹. The other solvents (all ACS grade) were dried and purified appropriately prior to use.

The synthesis and characterisation of both ligands 4,4'-diundecyl-2,2'-bipyridine and 4-methyl-4'-undecyl-2,2'-bipyridine have previously been described and are not repeated here [19]. $[\text{Ru}(2,2'\text{-bipy})_2\text{Cl}_2]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was also synthesized according to literature procedures [20]. The RuC11C11 complex was synthesized and characterized as is reported in ref. 21. The synthesis and characterization of RuC1C11 is described below.

For the characterization of the ruthenium compounds, IR infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Model 883 spectrophotometer (as liquid film supported on KBr discs) and NMR spectra were recorded using a Bruker Avance-300 spectrometer or a Bruker Avance-500 spectrometer with ¹³C{¹H} and ¹H shifts referenced to the residual solvent signals. All data were reported in ppm downfield from Si(CH₃)₄. Elemental analysis (C, H, N) was conducted by the Microanalytical Service of the University of Sevilla (CITIUS).

Synthesis of $[\text{Ru}(2,2'\text{-bipy})_2(4\text{-CH}_3\text{-}4'\text{-(C}_{11}\text{H}_{23})\text{-}2,2'\text{-bipy})][\text{PF}_6]_2$, RuC1C11.

The product was prepared by refluxing $[\text{Ru}(2,2'\text{-bipy})_2\text{Cl}_2]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.325 g, 0.62 mmol) and 4-methyl-4'-undecyl-2,2'-bipyridine (0.200 g, 0.62 mmol) in 30 mL of an ethanol solution for 18h. After this time, a solution of NH₄PF₆ (0.292 g, 1.85 mmol) in water (5

mL) was added to the reaction mixture at 0°C. Solvent was removed by evaporation in vacuum and the resulting residue washed with water and dried. Compound [Ru(2,2'-bipy)₂(4-CH₃-4'-(C₁₁H₂₃)-2,2'-bipy)][PF₆]₂ was obtained as solid orange material in good yield (0.56 g, 90 %). ¹H NMR (CD₃OD): δ 0.90 (t, *J*_{HH} = 6.9 Hz, 3H, CH₂CH₂(CH₂)₈CH₃), 1.28 (v br, 16H, CH₂CH₂(CH₂)₈CH₃), 1.65 (q, *J*_{HH} = 7.0 Hz, 2H, CH₂CH₂(CH₂)₈CH₃), 2.57 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.85 (t, *J*_{HH} = 7.4 Hz, 2H, CH₂CH₂(CH₂)₈CH₃), 7.32 (t, *J*_{HH} = 4.3 Hz, 2H, 5- and 5'-CH of alkyl-substituted bipy), 7.47 (m, 4H, 5- and 5'-CH of bipy), 7.62 (m, 2H, 6- and 6'-CH of alkyl-substituted bipy), 7.83 (m, 4H, 4- and 4'-CH of bipy), 8.09 (t, *J*_{HH} = 7.9 Hz, 4H, 6- and 6'-CH of bipy), 8.56 (d, *J*_{HH} = 9.9 Hz, 2H, 3- or 3'-CH of alkyl-substituted bipy), 8.66 (d, *J*_{HH} = 8.1 Hz, 4H, 3- and 3'-CH of bipy). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (CD₃OD): δ 16.9 (s, CH₂CH₂(CH₂)₉CH₂CH₃), 23.7 (s, CH₃), 26.3 (s, CH₂CH₂(CH₂)₉CH₂CH₃), 33.0 – 35.6 (several s, CH₂CH₂(CH₂)₉CH₂CH₃), 38.8 (s, CH₂CH₂(CH₂)₉CH₂CH₃), 128.0 – 132.3 (several s, 3- or 3'- or 5- or 5'-CH of bipy), 141.5 (s, 4- and 4'-CH of bipy), 154.1 – 155.2 (several s, 4- or 4'- or 6- or 6'-CH of bipy), 159.0 – 161.1 (several s, 2- or 2'-CH of bipy). Elemental analysis for C₄₂H₄₈F₁₂N₆P₂Ru: calc.: C, 49.1; H, 4.71; N, 8.18. Experimental: C, 49.3; H, 4.69; N, 8.14.

2.2 Methods.-

All measurements were done at pH=7 (cacodylate/NaCl buffer, I=0.01 mol dm⁻³) and 298.0±0.1 K.

2.2.1. Steady-state luminescence.-

Steady-state measurements were carried out in a spectrofluorimeter (Hitachi F-2500) interfaced to a PC for the reading and handling of the spectra. Quartz cells with optical paths of 10 mm were used.

The conditions depended on the type of measurement:

- a) Fluorescence titrations were performed at fixed ethidium bromide, EB, and DNA concentrations ($[EB]=3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[DNA]=2 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ for RuC11C11 and $[EB]=1.35 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[DNA]=9 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ for RuC1C11). Different surfactant concentrations were used in order to study the whole range of the molar ratio X desired ($X = [\text{surfactant}]/[\text{DNA}]$). The excitation and emission wavelengths were 500 nm and 590 nm, respectively. The excitation wavelength used was higher than that for ethidium bromide (480 nm) to avoid possible interferences in the emission intensity produced by the surfactants (see Figure I in Supporting Information).
- b) Fluorescence titrations were also performed using the fluorescent surfactant head as probe (without EB in the solution). A fixed concentration of $4.5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of both surfactants was used (this surfactant concentration is lower than the cmc for the two surfactants in order to avoid the presence of micelles in the solutions- see below). DNA concentration was varied from 5×10^{-8} to $2.1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ for RuC11C11 and from 3.2×10^{-8} to $2.1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ for RuC1C11 in order to study the whole range of X values. The excitation and emission wavelengths were 456 nm and 602 nm for the RuC11C11 complex and 457 nm and 602 nm for the RuC1C11 complex, respectively.

α -cyclodextrin concentration was maintained within the range from 1×10^{-6} to $2.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. For quenching measurements, the concentration of the quencher ($S_2O_8^{2-}$) was ranged from 0 to $3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

2.2.2. Circular dichroism spectra.-

Electronic circular dichroism (CD) spectra were recorded in a Biologic Mos-450 spectropolarimeter. A standard quartz cell of 10 mm path length was used. Scans were taken from 220 to 400 nm for the intrinsic region. Each spectrum was the average of 10 runs at a fixed temperature of 298.2K with a 5 min equilibration before each scan. The spectra obtained were expressed in terms of molar ellipticity.

Spectra were performed at fixed DNA and EB concentrations and varying the amount of the ruthenium surfactants in order to obtain the appropriate molar ratio X. The concentrations used were: [EB]= 9×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ and [DNA]= 2.5×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ for RuC11C11 and [EB]= 9×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ and [DNA]= 3.1×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ for RuC1C11.

2.2.3 AFM measurements.-

The images were obtained with a Molecular Imaging PicoPlus 2500 AFM (Agilent Technologies). Silicon cantilevers (Model Pointprobe, Nanoworld) with a resonance frequency around 240 KHz and nominal force constant 42 N/m were used. All AFM imaging was recording in air and in tapping mode, with scan speeds of about 0.5 Hz and data collection at 256x256 pixels.

In order to image isolated DNA molecules, it was necessary to use dilute solutions ($0.3 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$) due to the large size of these molecules. AFM images of the RuC1C11/DNA and RuC11C11/DNA complexes were obtained by drying a 30 μL droplet of surfactant and DNA solution deposited on the modified mica. For solution modification of the mica surface, 0.1% (v/v) APTES water solution was dropped onto a freshly cleaved mica surface, incubated for 20 min, the surface washed with ultra-pure water and then air dried. A total of 50 μL of DNA (or surfactant/DNA) solution was

dropped onto this modified surface, adsorbed for 30 min, washed with pure water and air dried for AFM imaging.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The critical micellar concentration, cmc, for the two ruthenium surfactants were obtained using fluorescence measurements. Figure 2 shows the dependence of the surfactant emission intensity on surfactant concentration for RuC1C11 and RuC11C11. The excitation wavelength was 456 nm for the double stranded surfactant and 457nm for the single stranded surfactant. The cmcs were obtained from the intersection point of the two linear plots observed, the results being $(5.0\pm 0.3)\times 10^{-7}$ mol dm⁻³ and $(3.0\pm 0.4)\times 10^{-6}$ mol dm⁻³ for RuC11C11 and RuC1C11, respectively. The cmc is lower for the double tailed surfactant due to the more negative Gibbs energy transfer contribution to the Gibbs energy of micellization. This term takes into account the Gibbs energy change accompanying the transfer of the hydrophobic chains from the solution into the micelle interior.

Information about the interaction between several species and DNA can be obtained studying the intercalation of the dye ethidium bromide (EB) in the polynucleotide [22]. The emission intensity of EB was measured in RuC1C11/DNA and RuC11C1/DNA solutions at different X values (see Figure 3). As can be seen, a decrease in the emission intensity is observed when the surfactant concentration increases. Note that the emission intensity of EB decreases to values close to zero, in agreement with its displacement to the aqueous phase. These results indicate that EB is displaced, in the presence of the surfactants, from its intercalative position to a more polar environment, the aqueous solution. Taking into account the strong affinity of the dye EB for locating between the stacked bases, this displacement can only be due to a

change in the structure of the polynucleotide caused by the interaction of the surfactants with the DNA.

Figure 3 also shows a sharper decrease of the EB emission intensity for the doubled stranded surfactant than for the single stranded surfactant. Taking into account the characteristics of the synthesized metallosurfactants, electrostatic attractive interactions between the positive heads of both surfactants and the negative phosphate residues of the DNA backbone are expected. The hydrophobic interactions among the tails of the surfactants and the polynucleotide, driven by the entropy of the counterion distribution [23], provoke a conformational modification in the DNA structure, generally related to the condensation of the DNA strands.

The dye EB, intercalated between the base pairs of a polynucleotide, shows a measured induced optical activity in circular dichroism exhibiting a positive dichroism band around 308 nm [24]. This band is measurable in our working conditions. When the metallosurfactants RuC1C11 and RuC11C11 are added to a solution containing DNA and EB, a decrease in such an induced band happens (see Figure II in Supporting Information). Figure 4 shows the decrease obtained in the molar ellipticity value of this induced band, at $\lambda = 308$ nm, for different X values. This result confirms the exit of the EB molecules from their intercalative position to the aqueous solution due to the interaction of the surfactants with the DNA. The decrease in the molar ellipticity is greater for the double stranded surfactant than for that of the single stranded. This fact supports the idea that a stronger interaction of RuC11C11 than of RuC1C11 with the polynucleotide takes places. It also demonstrates the importance of the hydrophobic interactions between the surfactants and the DNA since the head groups of the two surfactants have the same charge.

The metallosurfactants used in this work contain a metal centre in the polar head group. This centre, derived from the tris(2,2'-bipyridine)ruthenium (III) complex, possesses measurable light-responsive properties such as UV-vis absorption, emission intensity, redox potential, etc.[25]. Therefore, it is possible to get further insight about the surfactant-DNA interactions without the use of external dyes, which could modify the characteristics of the surfactant/DNA complexes. Bearing this in mind, the emission intensities of the two surfactants were measured at different X values (see Figure 5).

The same behavior for the two surfactants investigated was observed. Initially, an increase in X causes a decrease in the surfactant emission intensity and, after reaching a minimum, a further increment in X results in an increase of the emission intensity. In the authors' opinion, the initial decrease is due to the interaction of the surfactants with the polynucleotide, the surfactant/DNA complexes emitting less than the free surfactant molecules. These interactions, at high enough surfactant concentration, produce the total condensation of the polymer. The minimum in the emission intensity vs. [surfactant] plots would correspond to the X value (X_c) at which the condensation of the polymer is maximum; that is, when the DNA conformation changes from an elongated structure to a more compact globular structure. The minimum was observed at X values (X_c) of about 0.2 for RuC11C11 and 1 for RuC1C11. This result points out the importance of the hydrophobic interactions in the formation of surfactant/DNA complexes, in agreement with the results of circular dichroism and EB fluorescence previously obtained.

The increase in the surfactant emission intensities observed for X values higher than X_c could be due to the saturation of the surfactant-DNA interactions. An increase in the amount of *free* surfactant molecules would result in an increase in the emission

intensity. However, this increase shows a trend to reach a constant value, which could be explained by considering the formation of micellar aggregates in the solution.

In order to quantify the interaction of the metallosurfactants with DNA, a quantitative analysis of the results was done. For the process:

where S represents the surfactants, one can define the equilibrium constant as:

$$K_b = \frac{[S/DNA]}{[S_f][DNA_f]} \quad (2)$$

where S_f and DNA_f are the *free* surfactant and polynucleotide, respectively, and S/DNA is the surfactant/DNA complex. All concentrations refer to the total volume of the solution.

The K_b values for each DNA concentration can be determined from emission intensity measurements (EI) by using a two-state model [42]. On this basis the following equation can be written:

$$EI = \frac{EI_w + EI_{DNA} K_b [DNA_f]}{1 + K_b [DNA_f]} \quad (3)$$

Here EI_w and EI_{DNA} are the emission intensities of the free and totally bound surfactant, respectively. The free DNA concentration, related with the total DNA as follows,

$$[DNA_f] = [DNA_T] - [S/DNA] \quad (4)$$

can be calculated by using equations 5-7:

$$EI = \frac{EI_w [S]_w + EI_{DNA} [S/DNA]}{[S]_o} \quad (5)$$

$$EI = EI_w (100 - f_{(S/DNA)}) + EI_{DNA} f_{(S/DNA)} \quad (6)$$

$$[S/DNA] = [S]_o f_{(S/DNA)} \quad (7)$$

where $[S]_0$ is the total concentration of surfactant (the initial surfactant concentration) and $f_{(S/DNA)}$ the fraction (in percent) of surfactant interacting with the polynucleotide.

If the free DNA concentration is known, the binding constant can be calculated by using equation (3). The results obtained show a sigmoidal dependence of K_b with the total DNA concentration for the two metallosurfactants (see Figure 6). The decrease in the binding constant observed when the polynucleotide concentration increases confirms the typical cooperative character in the binding of cationic surfactants with DNA [27] (the interaction of a ligand with a receptor is cooperative when the binding of a first ligand to the receptor makes the binding of a second ligand to the same receptor stronger and so on).

In order to verify the accuracy of the procedure used, one must look at the minimum value of K_b obtained. This value corresponds to the binding constant of the metallosurfactants with DNA due principally to the electrostatic attraction forces between the positive head groups of the surfactants and the negative phosphate residues of the polynucleotide (it must be noted that non-electrostatic interactions such as hydrogen-bonds or Π -stacking could also take place between the ligands from surfactants head group and the polynucleotide). That is, this value does not depend on the hydrophobic chain of the surfactant (double or single). Effectively, the minimum K_b value obtained ($8.7 \times 10^5 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$ for RuC11C11 and RuC1C11) does not depend on the hydrophobic chain of the surfactant as was expected. Besides, this value agrees with the binding constant previously obtained in the interaction of the $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$ complex (without any hydrocarbon tail) with DNA ($8.0 \times 10^5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, see ref. 28).

The formation of hemimicelles (pseudomicellar aggregates) at the surface of the polymer plays a major role in the compaction of the polynucleotide. Addition of cyclic molecules which interact with the hydrophobic chain of the surfactants would make the

self-aggregation process of the surfactant more difficult and, therefore, the X value at which the condensation of the polynucleotide happens (X_c) could change. According to results obtained in a previous work [21], α -cyclodextrin (α -CD) interacts with the two metallosurfactants forming inclusion complexes, where the surfactant tails go into the host, the α -CD. The stoichiometries of the complexes surfactant/CD in aqueous solution are 1:1 and 1:2 for the two RuC1C11 and RuC11C11 surfactants [21]. Bearing this in mind, one can suppose that the presence of α -cyclodextrin in the solution can affect the value of X (X_c) at which the maximum condensation of DNA happens (the minimum in Figure 5). In this sense, the emission intensities of RuC11C11 and RuC1C11 were measured in the presence of DNA and different quantities of α -cyclodextrin. In all cases an initial decrease in the emission intensity of the surfactants was observed when X increases and, after reaching a minimum, a further increase in X caused an increase in the emission intensity as happens in the absence of cyclodextrin (see Figure III in Supporting Information). However, the value of X at which the minimum in the emission intensity is obtained varies depending on the cyclodextrin concentration. Figure 7A shows how the X_c value, obtained from the emission intensities of the surfactants, changes in the presence of different cyclodextrin concentrations for RuC1C11 and RuC11C11. X_c varies following a sigmoidal dependence. This behaviour is also confirmed from quenching measurements as will be later.

The variation in X_c can be explained by considering that the formation of surfactant-CD inclusion complexes hinders the surfactant-DNA interactions. Therefore, a higher surfactant concentration is necessary in order to compact the DNA in the presence of cyclodextrins. According to the results, the cyclodextrin concentration needed to decondense DNA is lower for RuC1C11 than for RuC11C11 (see Figure 7A).

This can be due to the stronger hydrophobic interaction among the chains and to DNA for the double stranded surfactant.

The quenching of the RuC11C11/DNA system, and of the RuC1C11/DNA system, by peroxodisulphate ions ($S_2O_8^{2-}$) has also been investigated in the presence and absence of α -cyclodextrin. The Stern-Volmer constants, K_{SV} , were obtained from the plots of the emission intensities ratio I_0/I versus the quencher concentration, at different X values (I_0 and I being the emission intensity of the metallosurfactants in the absence and presence of quencher, respectively). The relative K_{SV} values (relative to the value of K_{SV} for $X=0$) obtained from the slope of such plots for RuC11C11 are shown in Figure 7B. This Figure shows that an initial increase in X results in a decrease of K_{SV} , until a minimum is reached. A further increment of X leads to an increase in K_{SV} . At low X values, the surfactant/DNA complexes formed are expected to be negatively charged due to the high negative charge of the phosphate residues in DNA. This makes the approach between the ruthenium metallosurfactants, interacting with the polynucleotide, and the negatively charged $S_2O_8^{2-}$ ions more difficult and explains the initial decrease observed in K_{SV} . After the condensation of DNA occurs, at X_C , an increment in the X molar ratio is followed by an increase in the concentration of positively charged *free* surfactant molecules, which are more accessible to the peroxodisulfate ions. This will augment the quenching rate constant and, therefore, the K_{SV} constants. This explanation is supported by the X values for which the K_{SV} vs. X plots reach their minima. These values are ≈ 0.2 and 1.1 for RuC11C11 and RuC1C11 in the absence of cyclodextrin, respectively, which are similar to the X_C values found in Figure 5.

Besides, the X_C values obtained from Figure 7B are also similar to X_C values obtained from the emission intensities of the ruthenium surfactants (see Figure 7A) which increase when α -CD concentration augments (see Figures 7B).

With the aim of gaining further knowledge of metallosurfactant/DNA interactions, AFM topographic images of the surfactant/DNA complexes were obtained at different X molar ratios to confirm the DNA conformational changes predicted from other techniques. Figure IVA (in Supplementary Data) shows the image of pure DNA with its normal structure, an extended conformation or elongated coil. The addition of the metallosurfactants provokes the total compaction of the polynucleotide at X=0.2 for RuC11C11 and X=1 for RuC1C11 as is observed in Figures 8A and 8B. A partial condensation of the strands is clearly seen for lower X values (Figures IVB and IVD in Supplementary Data). The condensation remains for higher X values (Figures IVC and IVE in Supplementary Data). According to the AFM images, the addition of metallosurfactants produces the bending of the DNA strands with the formation of different loops which, finally, results in globules.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Two metallosurfactants derived from $[\text{Ru}(2,2'\text{-bpy})_3]^{2+}$ were synthesized and characterized. Their interaction with DNA and the effect they exert on the conformation of the polynucleotide were studied using different techniques. Results show DNA is condensed when a determined surfactant concentration is added to the solution. The formation of micellar aggregates (hemimicelles), due to the forces of electrostatic attraction between the cationic head groups of the surfactant and the anionic phosphate residues of the polynucleotide and to the hydrophobic interactions among the surfactant's tails, favors the conformational change. The binding equilibrium constants corresponding to the interaction of the metallosurfactants with DNA were obtained for different molar ratio $X = [\text{surfactant}]/[\text{DNA}]$. The sigmoidal trend that these equilibrium constants show with X confirms the cooperative character of the binding. The

hydrophobic interactions between the hydrocarbon chains of the surfactant and the polynucleotide, as well as the ionic correlation effect produced by the counterions that diminishes the repulsion among the phosphate groups of the polynucleotide, cause the compaction of the DNA, that is, a conformational change in the polymer from an elongated double helix structure to a compact globule state. The addition of cyclodextrin to a solution containing surfactant/DNA complexes provokes the decompaction of the polynucleotide. This demonstrates the importance of the hydrophobic interactions in the condensation process of DNA.

From comparison of the results shown in this work to those previously obtained for other cationic surfactants, influence of the surfactant nature on the DNA compaction process can be discussed. The metallosurfactants used here have hydrophobic tails with 12 methylene groups. However, compaction of the polynucleotide with RuC11C11 happens at an X value lower than those obtained for surfactants with longer hydrophobic chains [29]. The presence of two hydrocarbon chains in the surfactant favors the formation of hemimicelles (micellar aggregates) on the DNA backbone and makes condensation of the polynucleotide easier. The charge (and perhaps the size, although this must still be proven) of the head groups also influences such phenomenon. A higher charge of the ionic head of the surfactant provokes an increase in the electrostatic interaction between the cationic surfactant and the negative phosphate groups of the polynucleotide. Besides, the ion correlation effect produced by the presence of a higher concentration of counterions in the solution (bigger than for monovalent surfactants) causes a significant diminution of the repulsion among the phosphate groups of the DNA favouring the condensation phenomenon. Indeed, the use of cationic surfactants with a high charge in their polar head group improves characteristics of the reagents to be used in gene therapy.

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FIGURES

Figure 1. Structures of the surfactants $[\text{Ru}(2,2'\text{-bipy})_2(4,4'\text{-(C}_{11}\text{H}_{23})_2\text{-}2,2'\text{-bipy})]^{2+}$ (RuC11C11) and $[\text{Ru}(2,2'\text{-bipy})_2(4\text{-(CH}_3\text{)-}4'\text{-(C}_{11}\text{H}_{23})\text{-}2,2'\text{-bipy})]^{2+}$ (RuC1C11).

Figure 2. Plot of EI (emission intensity) of the surfactants ($\lambda_{\text{em}} = 602\text{nm}$) versus the surfactant concentration for RuC11C11 and RuC1C11. The intersection point of the lines indicates the cmc for each surfactant ($T = 298 \pm 0.1\text{K}$, $I = 0.01\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\text{pH} = 7$). Error bars represent standard deviation in each x coordinate value ($n = 5$).

Figure 3. Plot of the ratio emission intensity/surfactant concentration of the fluorescent ruthenium surfactants versus the X molar ratio ($T=298\pm 0.1\text{K}$ and $\text{pH}=7$). Error bars represent standard deviation in each X value ($n=5$).

Figure 4. Dependence of the relative molar ellipticity of EB (at $\lambda=308\text{ nm}$) with the molar ratio X for RuC11C11 and RuC1C11. $[\theta]$ and $[\theta]_0$ represent the molar ellipticity of EB in a DNA solution with and without surfactant, respectively ($T=298\pm 0.1\text{K}$, $I=0.01\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\text{pH}=7$). Error bars represent standard deviation in each X value ($n=10$).

Figure 5. Emission intensity values of RuC11C11 and RuC1C11 at different X values ($T=298\pm 0.1\text{K}$, $I= 0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\text{pH}=7$). Error bars represent standard deviation in each x value ($n=5$).

Figure 6. Sigmoidal dependence of K_b with the DNA concentration for RuC11C11. Points represent experimental values and the line the best fit obtained by using equation 2 ($T=298\pm 0.1\text{K}$, $I= 0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\text{pH}=7$). Error bars represent standard deviation in each x value ($n=5$).

Figure 7. (A) Variation of the X_c values, obtained from emission intensities of RuC11C11 and RuC1C11, at different α -cyclodextrin concentrations. Square symbols correspond to X_c values obtained from quenching measurements. (B) Stern-Volmer constants obtained for the process RuC11C11 + $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ in the presence of different cyclodextrin concentrations. ($T=298\pm 0.1\text{K}$, $I= 0.01\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\text{pH}=7$). Error bars in the two Figures represent standard deviation in each x value ($n=5$ for Figures A and B).

Figure 8. AFM topographic image of calf thymus DNA adsorbed on APTES-modified mica surface in the presence of the metallosurfactants (A: RuC11C11 $X=0.2$ and B: RuC1C11 $X=1$) ($T=298\pm 0.1\text{K}$, $I= 0.01\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\text{pH}=7$).